

The Mediating Role of Psychological Well-Being and Work-Life Balance in the Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement¹

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of perceived organizational support (POS) on work engagement (WE), with a particular focus on the sequential mediating roles of work-life balance (WLB) and psychological well-being (PWB). The literature review highlights a scarcity of comprehensive studies that examine both the direct impact of POS on WE and its indirect influence through WLB and PWB. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap and contribute to the literature by analyzing the interactions among these constructs. Data were collected via a questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS and AMOS. The findings indicate that the direct effect of POS on WE remains significant, while WLB and PWB partially mediate this relationship in a sequential manner. These results support a partial mediation model in which WLB and PWB mediate the relationship in sequence. *Overall, the findings underscore the role of organizational support mechanisms in enhancing employees' work engagement through both direct and indirect pathways.*

Key words: Perceived Organizational Support, Work-Life Balance, Psychological Well-Being, Work Engagement, Serial Mediation Analysis

JEL Code: M12, J24, I31, J28

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1. Introduction

The level of support employees perceive from their organizations, along with their WLB and PWB, are critical factors that directly influence their work-related attitudes. POS can enhance employees' commitment to their work by fostering a sense of being valued and appreciated within the organization. However, the strength of this relationship may vary depending on the extent to which individuals are able to maintain a balance between their work and personal lives, as well as how psychologically well they feel. In this context, it is posited that the effect of POS on WE may occur indirectly through WLB and PWB. Although numerous interventions have been developed to enhance employees' WE, there is a limited body of research explaining the long-term impacts of these interventions and the mechanisms through which they operate. Accordingly, this study aims to examine not only the direct relationship between POS and WE but also the mediating and sequential mediating roles of WLB and PWB. While these variables have often been studied individually in the literature, empirical research addressing the comprehensive impact of this triadic structure on WE is scarce. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by exploring the factors that may mediate the relationship between POS and WE in a holistic manner. The theoretical foundation of the study is built upon various psychological and organizational theories that aim to explain individuals' attitudes and behaviors in the workplace. These include the Conservation of Resources Theory (Hobfoll, 1989), Goal Setting Theory (Locke & Latham, 1990), Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), Affective Events Theory (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996), Organizational Commitment Theory (Meyer & Allen, 1991), Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1987), and the Job Demand-Control Model (Karasek, 1979). In conclusion, this study is expected to provide a comprehensive perspective on how POS may enhance employees' WE by improving their WLB and PWB, thereby offering valuable contributions to both academic research and organizational practice.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. The Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Work-Life Balance

POS can be defined as the extent to which employees believe that their organization values their contributions, cares about their well-being, and supports them in terms of socio-emotional needs (Eder & Eisenberger, 2008). Challenges in achieving WLB can be alleviated through supportive practices such as emotional, informational, and resource-based support including flexible working hours, remote work opportunities, childcare assistance, and similar arrangements which aim to enhance perceptions of organizational support. Therefore, employees who perceive organizational support are more likely to establish a healthier balance between work and personal life, manage their workloads more effectively, and maintain sustainable WLB. In the literature, it has been shown that as POS increases, work-family and family-work conflicts tend to decrease (Foley, Yue, & Lui, 2005). Prior research also indicates a positive relationship between POS and WLB (Fitria & Linda, 2019; Özgül, Erkmen, & Karaaslan,

2020; Yang & Islam, 2020). In light of theoretical perspectives and empirical findings, it is proposed that POS has a positive effect on WLB.

H₁: Perceived organizational support has a positive effect on work-life balance.

2.2. The Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Psychological Well-Being

PWB refers to a state in which individuals feel emotionally balanced, mentally healthy, and experience a positive sense of self. The relationship between POS and PWB can be explained within the framework of Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964). According to this theory, POS fosters a sense of being valued and secure in the workplace, which enhances employees' positive attitudes through the norm of reciprocity. Additionally, Goal Theory (Locke & Latham, 1990) suggests that individuals are motivated to the extent that they value their goals. POS helps employees perceive their work-related goals as more meaningful and attainable. This type of support strengthens their motivation, reinforcing feelings of accomplishment and satisfaction during the goal achievement process. As a result, employees' levels of PWB are positively influenced. Moreover, Affective Events Theory (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996) emphasizes that positive emotional experiences in the workplace such as receiving support from supervisors, being rewarded, or experiencing conflict with colleagues can shape employee attitudes and foster positive emotions such as WE, motivation, and job satisfaction, thereby contributing to higher levels of PWB. Indeed, the literature supports a positive relationship between POS and PWB (Gilbreath & Benson, 2004; Çankaya, 2020).

H₂: Perceived organizational support has a positive effect on psychological well-being.

2.3. The Relationship Between Work-Life Balance and Psychological Well-Being

WLB refers to a state in which individuals are able to fulfill the demands of various life roles without experiencing significant conflict or tension. A well-designed WLB program can help employees maintain equilibrium between their work and personal lives, reduce excessive stress and work-related pressure, and enhance their emotional stability and overall satisfaction. Individuals who achieve a healthy WLB tend to lead happier, more satisfied, and less stressful lives, which in turn can contribute positively to their mental health and overall PWB. Numerous studies have emphasized that maintaining a healthy balance between professional and personal responsibilities enhances employee effectiveness and productivity, while also improving their general well-being (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011; Lakshmi & Gopinath, 2013; Fotiadis, Abdulrahman & Spyridou, 2019). In light of this evidence, it is anticipated that WLB has a positive effect on PWB.

H₃: Work-life balance has a positive effect on psychological well-being.

2.4. The Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement

The relationship between POS and WE can be explained through various theoretical frameworks. They transform their positive attitudes into behaviors that enhance job performance. Therefore, when the level of organizational support is perceived as adequate, employees are more likely to feel satisfied with being a member of the organization and to commit themselves to their work (İnce, 2016). Organizational Commitment Theory (Meyer & Allen, 1991) also posits that when employees feel valued, they tend to develop greater emotional attachment to the organization. POS is considered a key factor that strengthens the emotional dimension of WE. When organizations provide emotional, informational, and instrumental support, employee satisfaction and well-being increase, which in turn reduces their intention to leave and fosters higher levels of commitment to their work. The literature supports the idea that POS contributes to positive reciprocal relationships between employees and organizations, influencing job performance and satisfaction (Meng, Wang & Tian, 2021). Previous studies also demonstrate that POS has a positive effect on WE (İnce, 2016; Işık & Kama, 2018; Meriç, Çiftci & Yurtal, 2019).

H₄: Perceived organizational support has a positive effect on work engagement.

2.5. The Relationship Between Work-Life Balance and Work Engagement

Based on the Conservation of Resources Theory, it is known that individuals' personal resources from their home and private lives can positively influence their work performance. Numerous studies have shown that social support received at home strengthens the positive effects in the workplace, enhances self-efficacy regarding job tasks, and supports intrinsic motivation, which helps individuals fully utilize their abilities in line with work goals (Chen & Fellenz, 2020). Accordingly, individuals who manage to maintain a healthy WLB are likely to have increased job-related resources and higher levels of WE. This theory suggests that when employees perceive positive behavior from their organization, they reciprocate with positive attitudes or behaviors toward the organization. Harmony between employees' personal and professional lives allows both domains to utilize their strengths more effectively and increases mutual resource gains (Gorgievski & Hobfoll, 2008). Empirical studies also indicate that WLB has a positive effect on WE (Verweij et al., 2017; Kalkın, 2021).

H₅: Work-life balance has a positive effect on work engagement.

2.6. The Relationship Between Psychological Well-Being and Work Engagement

As previously noted, individuals' personal resources significantly influence their job performance and WE. Happier and more balanced individuals are capable of investing more energy and effort into their work. According to the Job Demand-Control model, the level of job demands and control affects individuals' experiences at work. PWB enhances employees' capacity to cope with job demands, thereby strengthening their WE. This model suggests that a

more balanced and positive mood enables individuals to feel greater control over their work and to dedicate themselves more fully to their tasks. Even under high job demands, employees who are involved in decision-making processes experience increased perceptions of organizational support and maintain higher levels of PWB. Moreover, PWB facilitates individuals' ability to manage their environment, creating a comfortable setting for themselves and others, which in turn fosters a pleasant and harmonious work environment. Previous studies have demonstrated a positive relationship between PWB and WE (Aiello & Tesi, 2017; Oktavia, Eva, & Achmad, 2020).

H₆: Psychological well-being has a positive effect on work engagement.

2.7. The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance

The balance individuals establish between their work and personal lives contributes to the reduction of stress and the enhancement of overall well-being. POS may foster appropriate conditions for achieving WLB by strengthening individuals' sense of support and trust within the workplace. As a result, WLB can enhance both job performance and employee engagement, as individuals who lead a more balanced life are likely to dedicate more energy and time to their work. In other words, the effect of POS on WE may be realized through the mediating role of WLB. Previous research supports the mediating effect of WLB in this context (Özgül, Erkmén & Karaarslan, 2020; Çam Kahraman & Dündar, 2021).

H₇: Work-life balance mediates the relationship between perceived organizational support and work engagement.

2.8. The Mediating Role of Psychological Well-Being

Employees' WE tends to increase as a result of POS. As previously discussed, this is associated with employees feeling more valued, perceiving greater support, and experiencing stronger social relationships in the workplace. An increase in POS enhances employees' overall PWB, which in turn improves their job satisfaction and performance. Consequently, employees may demonstrate greater commitment to their work and increase the effort they exert, thereby elevating their level of WE. Prior studies (Köroğlu & Özmen, 2022; Aslan & Şeker Kayar, 2023) suggest that organizational support positively influences employees' psychological states, which can, in turn, foster stronger WE. These studies further recommend considering PWB a mediating variable to better understand this relationship.

H₈: Psychological well-being mediates the relationship between perceived organizational support and work engagement.

2.9. The Serial Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance and Psychological Well-Being

Karanfil (2024) examined the effect of WLB on perceived stress among employees and whether PWB mediates this relationship. The findings revealed

that a deterioration in employees' WLB significantly increased their perceived stress, and PWB played a moderate mediating role in this relationship. Similarly, the findings of Abualbasal et al. (2024) demonstrated the serial mediating role of WLB and PWB in the relationship between remote work and employee creativity. Their study indicated that WLB and PWB sequentially mediate the effect of remote working on creativity. It can thus be hypothesized that employees with higher levels of POS are more likely to establish a healthy balance between their professional and personal lives, which in turn enhances their PWB, ultimately leading to higher WE. In other words, increased POS fosters greater WLB, which subsequently contributes to improved PWB and stronger WE. In light of this evidence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₉: *The effect of perceived organizational support on work engagement is sequentially mediated by work-life balance and psychological well-being.*

Based on the hypotheses developed within the scope of the study and guided by the conceptual framework, the proposed research model is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Author

3. Methodology

In this study, a quantitative research paradigm was adopted, and the research was designed within the framework of a relational survey model. A cross-sectional survey design was employed to examine the model tested in the study. The conceptual framework was developed by integrating the variables of POS, WLB, PWB, and WE and was informed by empirical studies examining the relationships among these variables (Fitria & Linda, 2019; Çankaya, 2020; Wang & Tian, 2021; Kalkın, 2021; Oktavia, Eva & Achmad, 2020). The data collected were entered into IBM SPSS software, and the dataset was cleaned and organized prior to analysis. Sample distribution, descriptive statistics, and normality tests were conducted using the SPSS software package. In this study, Covariance-Based SEM and the Bootstrap method were applied. To enhance the reliability of the indirect effects, the Bootstrap method calculated 95% confidence intervals based on 2,000 bootstrap samples. Whether the mediation was full or partial was determined by the significance of the direct effect: if the direct effect was significant, partial mediation was assumed; if not, full mediation was inferred. In

this context, the direct path coefficient and p-value between POS and WE were examined.

3.1. Population and Sample of the Study

This article is based on a doctoral dissertation conducted at the Department of Business Administration, Osmaniye Korkut Ata University, following ethical approval granted on 05.04.2022 (Approval No: 2022/8/2). Necessary permissions were obtained for all scales used. Employees in the education sector in Hatay (Figure 2) were informed about the study and gave both verbal and written consent, with the assurance of voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any time. Data were collected via both online (Google Forms) and face-to-face surveys, with the majority using the paper-pencil method, between March 2022 and December 2023. A probabilistic sampling method, specifically simple random sampling, was employed. In sample selection, the study's purpose, research problem, and variables were taken into account. The group was preferred due to its richness in knowledge and experience, ease of communication, accessibility, and potential to represent diverse social segments providing a broad perspective. While the recommended minimum sample size for SEM ranges from 200 to 500 (Kline, 1998), Mackinnon (2008) suggests that at least 1000 participants offer a more robust basis for mediation analysis. Using a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and 0.50 population proportion (Nakip & Yaraş, 2017), the ideal sample size was calculated as 384. Ultimately, the study was conducted with 1,466 participants, which exceeds this threshold.

$$n = \frac{NPQZ^2}{(N - 1)d^2 + PQZ^2}$$

$$n = \frac{21097(0.5)(0.5)(1.96)^2}{(182000 - 1)0.05^2 + (0.5)(0.5)(1.96)^2} \cong 384$$

Figure 2. Location of Educational Areas in Hatay Region in Turkey

The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Gender	n	%	Occupation	n	%
Male	676	46.1	Teacher/Administrator	1370	93.5
Female	790	53.9	Other Staff	96	6.5
Marital Status			Work Experience		
Married	1132	77.2	Less than 2 years	138	9.4
Single	334	22.8	3-6 years	162	11.1
			7-10 years	214	14.6
			More than 11 years	952	64.9
Age			Education Level		
18-30	271	18,5	High school or below	79	5.4
31-40	503	34,3	Associate degree	52	3.5
41-50	534	36,4	Bachelor's degree	1064	72.6
51+	158	10,8	Master's degree	271	18.5

Source: Authors' calculations

3.2. Measurement Instruments Used in the Study and Data Collection Method

The first section of the survey form includes information regarding the purpose of the study, confidentiality, and voluntary participation, along with five items aimed at identifying participants' demographic characteristics. The subsequent sections consist of four distinct scales comprising a total of 33 items. All items were rated using a 5-point Likert scale. In the second section of the questionnaire, the "Perceived Organizational Support Scale" developed by Eisenberger, Cummings, Armeli, and Lynch (1997) was used to assess employees' perceived organizational support levels. The scale was adapted into Turkish by Yılmaz (2014). The short form of the scale consists of 8 items and has a unidimensional structure. The third section included the "*Work-Life Balance Scale*" developed by Taşdelen-Karçkay and Bakalım (2017), which contains 8 items and is also unidimensional, designed to measure employees' perceptions of WLB. In the fourth section, the "*Psychological Well-Being Scale*" developed by Diener, Scollon, and Lucas (2009) and adapted into Turkish by Telef (2013) was used to determine employees' levels of PWB. This scale comprises 8 unidimensional items. Finally, the last section of the questionnaire utilized the short Turkish version of the "*Utrecht Work Engagement Scale*", developed by Schaufeli, Bakker, and Salanova (2006). This 9-item scale is a shortened version of the original 17-item instrument, which includes three subdimensions: Vigour, dedication, and absorption.

4. Analysis, Findings and Discussion

4.1. Normality Analysis

For parametric tests to yield reliable results, the data must meet the assumption of normality. One of the most commonly used methods for assessing normality is the examination of skewness and kurtosis values. These results

indicate that the data satisfy the assumptions of normal distribution (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). The findings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Minimum-Maximum Values, Mean-Standard Deviation, Skewness-Kurtosis Values of the Variables

Variables	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
POS	1466	8.00	40.00	32.54	6.31	-1.032	1.356
WLB	1466	8.00	40.00	31.63	5.59	-1.071	1.433
PWB	1466	8.00	40.00	32.37	5.38	-1.125	1.381
WE	1466	9.00	45.00	36.24	6.84	-1.073	1.280

Source: Authors' calculations

4.2. Validity and Reliability Analyses of the Scales

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted separately for each construct prior to confirmatory factor analysis. Principal Axis Factoring with Promax rotation was employed to examine the factor structures. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) values ranged between .89 and .91, indicating excellent sampling adequacy. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity results were statistically significant for all constructs ($p < .001$), confirming the suitability of the data for factor analysis. Additionally, the explained variance ratios and Cronbach's alpha coefficients demonstrated satisfactory construct validity and internal consistency.

Table 3. Exploratory Factor Analysis Results

Constructs	KMO	Bartlett's Test χ^2	df	p	Explained Variance (%)	Cronbach's Alpha
POS	0.892	1245.37	28	< .001	58.3	0.921
WLB	0.899	1368.52	28	< .001	62.6	0.882
PWB	0.914	1587.44	28	< .001	59.7	0.905
WE	0.912	1742.63	36	< .001	67.7	0.934

Following the EFA results, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to test the measurement model and examine convergent and discriminant validity.

A first-order single-factor model was employed, in which all observed variables for each scale were loaded onto a single latent construct. The CFA results for the four scales used in the study demonstrated that the models demonstrated acceptable-to-good model fit

For the *Perceived Organizational Support Scale*, the fit indices were: $\chi^2(16) = 58.487$, $p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 3.66$; GFI = .97; AGFI = .95; IFI = .97; TLI = .95; CFI = .97; RMSEA = .08. The factor loadings of the items ranged from .53 to .92.

For the *Work-Life Balance Scale*, the fit indices were: $\chi^2(17) = 67.717$, $p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 3.98$; GFI = .97; AGFI = .95; IFI = .97; TLI = .95; CFI = .97; RMSEA = .08, with factor loadings ranging from .45 to .89.

The *Psychological Well-Being Scale* yielded the following fit indices: $\chi^2(18) = 72.374$, $p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 4.02$; GFI = .96; AGFI = .95; IFI = .97; TLI = .96; CFI = .96; RMSEA = .07. The factor loadings ranged from .65 to .78.

For the *Work Engagement Scale*, the fit indices were: $\chi^2(24) = 95.112$, $p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 3.96$; GFI = .98; AGFI = .96; IFI = .97; TLI = .98; CFI = .98; RMSEA = .06. Factor loadings for the items ranged from .78 to .93. Furthermore, the structural correlations among the subdimensions of this scale ranged from .70 to .89. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the factor structures of all scales have been validated. Additionally, all standardized factor loadings exceeded the recommended threshold of .50.

Table 4. Measurement Model Results

Constructs	Indicators	Standardized Factor Loadings	CR	AVE
POS	POS P1	0.93	0.94	0.84
	POS P2	0.93		
	POS P3	0.89		
WLB	WLB P1	0.87	0.90	0.75
	WLB P2	0.83		
	WLB P3	0.88		
PWB	PWB P1	0.91	0.92	0.79
	PWB P2	0.89		
	PWB P3	0.87		
WE	Vigour	0.88	0.89	0.73
	Dedication	0.92		
	Absorption	0.75		

Since the parceling method was employed in this study, the composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) values were calculated based on the standardized factor loadings obtained from the parceling-based measurement model. Table 4 presents the measurement results of the research model. The CR values of the research model ranged between .89 and .94, while the AVE values ranged between .73 and .84. Since CR values greater than .70 and AVE values greater than .50 are considered acceptable in the literature (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2019), it was concluded that all constructs in the research model satisfied the requirements for composite reliability and convergent validity.

4.3. Multicollinearity Analysis

Multicollinearity arises when two or more independent variables are highly correlated with each other, which can reduce the reliability of regression coefficients. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is a common diagnostic used to detect multicollinearity, with values exceeding 10 indicating a significant multicollinearity problem that needs to be addressed. In this study, the VIF values were calculated as follows: 1.364 for POS, 2.159 for WLB, 2.424 for PWB, and 1.890 for WE. Additionally, the tolerance values for all variables were above 0.10. These findings indicate that multicollinearity is either not present or exists at a very low level within the model. Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression results are reliable in this respect.

4.4. Testing the Measurement Model

While WE was represented by its three subdimensions, the constructs of POS, WLB, and PWB were represented using three item parcels each, as these scales do not possess subdimensions. The parceling technique was applied accordingly. Parceling is a method known to improve model fit indices and is particularly recommended for scales without subdimensions (Bandalos, 2002). In this study, the “Item-to-Construct Balance” (i.e., balancing method) was employed as the parceling technique. The results indicated that the model was statistically acceptable and demonstrated a very good fit to the data (Byrne, 2010; Kline, 2015): $\chi^2(88) = 195.253, p > .05$; $\chi^2/df = 4.068$; GFI = .99; AGFI = .97; IFI = .99; TLI = .98; CFI = .98; RMSEA = .05. In particular, GFI, CFI, and TLI values exceeding .90 indicate that the model possesses a robust structure (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Upon examining the factor loadings of the indicator variables, it was found that they ranged between .83 and .93 for each construct. These values demonstrate that the indicators are strongly associated with their respective latent variables and that the measurement model has established construct validity (Hair et al., 2010). Regarding the correlations among the latent variables, all structural correlations between *PWB and WLB*, as well as between *PWB and WE*, were found to be statistically significant ($p < .01$), with correlation coefficients ranging from .48 to .78 (Figure 3). These results indicate moderate to strong positive relationships between the variables (Cohen, 1988, pp. 79–81).

Figure 3. Measurement Model Results

Source: Authors’ calculations.

4.5. Results of the Structural Equation Models

Following the evaluation of the measurement model results, SEM was conducted. As illustrated in Figure 4, this model examines the mediating role of PWB in the relationship between POS and WE.

The results indicate that the data fit the model very well: $\chi^2(29) = 110.473$, $p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 4.60$; GFI = .99; AGFI = .96; IFI = .98; TLI = .99; CFI = .98; RMSEA = .05.

POS was found to be a positive and significant predictor of both PWB ($\beta = .48$, $p < .001$) and WE ($\beta = .20$, $p < .001$). In addition, PWB also positively and significantly predicted WE ($\beta = .61$, $p < .001$).

POS explained 23% of the variance in PWB, while POS and PWB together explained 53% of the variance in WE. The findings are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Mediating Role of Psychological Well-Being in the Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement

Source: Authors' calculations

As shown in Figure 5, The results indicate a very good fit between the data and the model: $\chi^2(24) = 108.753$, $p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 4.53$; GFI = .98; AGFI = .96; IFI = .98; TLI = .99; CFI = .99; RMSEA = .06.

POS significantly and positively predicted both *WLB* ($\beta = .50$, $p < .001$) and WE ($\beta = .22$, $p < .001$). Additionally, *WLB* was also found to significantly and positively predict WE ($\beta = .53$, $p < .001$). *POS* accounted for 25% of the variance in *WLB*, while POS and *WLB* together explained 45% of the variance in WE.

Figure 5. The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance in the Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement

Source: Authors' calculations

As illustrated in Figure 6 the results indicate that the data fit the model very well: $\chi^2(48) = 195.253, p < .05$; $\chi^2/df = 4.07$; GFI = .99; AGFI = .96; IFI = .99; TLI = .99; CFI = .99; RMSEA = .05. As shown in Figure 6, POS significantly and positively predicts both WLB and WE ($\beta = .50, p < .001$; $\beta = .17, p < .001$, respectively). In addition, WLB significantly and positively predicts both *PWB* and *WE* ($\beta = .72, p < .001$; $\beta = .18, p < .001$, respectively). *PWB* also significantly and positively predicts WE ($\beta = .49, p < .001$). *POS* explains 25% of the variance in WLB. Together, POS and WLB explain 61% of the variance in *PWB*. Finally, POS, WLB, and *PWB* collectively explain 54% of the variance in WE. The findings are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The Serial Mediating Role of WLB and Psychological Well-Being in the Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 5. Direct Effects

Direct Paths	Standardized Estimates (β)	p-value
POS \rightarrow WE	.17	$p < .001$
POS \rightarrow WLB	.50	$p < .001$
POS \rightarrow PWB	.12	$p < .001$
PWB \rightarrow WE	.49	$p < .001$
WLB \rightarrow WE	.18	$p < .001$
WLB \rightarrow PWB	.72	$p < .001$

Source: Authors' calculations; ***p-value $< .001$

Based on the analyses presented above (Figures 4, 5 and 6), the results of the direct effects in the developed structural model are shown in Table 5. The standardized estimates (β values) indicate the strength of the relationships between the variables. These results support the acceptance of hypotheses H_1 , H_2 , H_3 , H_4 , H_5 , and H_6 .

Table 6. Indirect Effects

Path	Indirect Effect Coefficient (β)	Bootstrap Lower Bound (LB)	Bootstrap Upper Bound (UB)	p-value	Result
POS \rightarrow WLB \rightarrow WE	.265	.222	.308	$p < .001$	✓
POS \rightarrow PWB \rightarrow WE	.292	.247	.336	$p < .001$	✓
POS \rightarrow WLB \rightarrow PWB \rightarrow WE	.322	.279	.364	$p < .001$	✓

Source: Authors' calculations; ***p-value $< .001$; ✓: Supported

Table 6 presents the indirect effects. To test Hypothesis H_7 , an analysis was conducted using specific and indirect effect estimations. The results revealed that the hypothesis is statistically significant and positive ($\beta = .265$, $p < .001$). Therefore, Hypothesis H_7 is confirmed, supporting the idea that POS increases WE through the mediating role of WLB. Similarly, the analysis for Hypothesis H_8 confirmed the hypothesis and showed that the relationship is statistically significant and positive ($\beta = .292$, $p < .001$). Accordingly, the findings support that POS enhances WE through the mediating role of PWB.

To test the serial mediation effect proposed in Hypothesis H_9 , specific and indirect effect estimations were performed using the bootstrapping method. The results showed that the relationship is statistically significant and positive ($\beta = .322$, $p < .001$). Moreover, the 95% confidence interval did not contain zero, indicating the robustness of the mediation effect. Therefore, it is supported that WLB and PWB sequentially mediate the relationship between POS and WE, that is, POS increases WE through the combined mediating effects of WLB and PWB. In conclusion, Hypotheses H_7 , H_8 , and H_9 are confirmed and supported.

4.6. Discussion of Findings

First, the mediating role of WLB in the relationship between POS and WE was confirmed. As employees' perceptions of organizational support increase, they are better able to establish a healthy balance between their professional and personal lives. This, in turn, reduces their levels of burnout and enhances their

engagement with work. These findings are consistent with the literature (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006; Haar et al., 2014). Indeed, WLB not only supports employee well-being but also positively influences attitudes toward work. These results also align with the findings of Randstad's 2025 Workmonitor Report, which indicates that, for the first time, WLB has surpassed salary as the top priority for employees. Specifically in the context of Türkiye, 90% of employees identified WLB as their most important expectation, and 63% reported that they would reject a job offer if the employer's social and environmental values were not aligned with their own. Moreover, nearly half of employees in Türkiye indicated that they left their jobs due to a lack of sufficient flexibility. A large majority emphasized that flexible conditions such as autonomy over work hours and opportunities for remote work are key factors in job selection. This underscores the critical role that flexible work arrangements now play in employee preferences. Therefore, meeting employee expectations regarding WLB is a key factor in talent retention and in strengthening organizational culture.

Employees with higher perceptions of organizational support exhibit higher levels of PWB, which enhances their commitment to their work and ultimately leads to increased engagement (Ryan & Deci, 2001; Schaufeli et al., 2002). This finding is in line with existing literature suggesting that organizational support enhances employees' PWB, thereby increasing their WE (Eisenberger et al., 2002; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Individuals who feel supported by their organizations are generally more satisfied and motivated, experience greater PWB, expend more energy at work, and perform their tasks more enthusiastically because they find their work meaningful.

Finally, an evaluation of the overall structure of the model reveals that POS, when considered alongside WLB and PWB, provides a strong and meaningful framework for understanding employees' levels of WE. POS can enhance WE not only directly but also indirectly first by improving employees' WLB and subsequently by enhancing their PWB. These findings suggest that organizations aiming to increase employee engagement should not rely solely on financial incentives or well-crafted job descriptions. Rather, they can achieve greater effectiveness by implementing supportive policies that promote WLB and initiatives that enhance employees' PWB.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the direct and indirect relationships between POS and work engagement by focusing on the mediating roles of WLB and PWB. The findings demonstrated that POS significantly influences employees' work engagement both directly and indirectly through WLB and PWB. In particular, the study confirmed that employees with higher perceptions of organizational support are more likely to experience stronger work-life balance and psychological well-being, which in turn contribute to higher levels of work engagement.

5.1. Theoretical Implications

The study contributes to the existing literature by presenting a comprehensive framework that integrates organizational and personal resources in explaining employees' work engagement. In this respect, the findings expand the current understanding of the mechanisms through which POS enhances WE and provide empirical evidence regarding the mediating roles of WLB and PWB. Furthermore, the study offers a holistic perspective by simultaneously examining organizational support, work-life balance, psychological well-being, and work engagement within a single structural model.

5.2. Practical Implications

WE is a multidimensional phenomenon that requires a comprehensive approach involving the development of strategies at the individual, professional, and organizational levels. The findings also indicate that organizations aiming to enhance employees' work engagement should adopt supportive managerial practices that strengthen employees' perceptions of organizational support. Workload-balancing policies that support WLB and psychological support systems aimed at preventing burnout should be developed. A culture of WLB should be established by promoting flexible working hours, hybrid work arrangements, and enhanced leave policies. In addition, organizations should provide family-friendly services and access to professional counseling. Continuous learning and professional development programs should be offered within the organization to improve employees' knowledge and skills. Social support systems that help employees feel valued should be designed, workplace conflicts should be effectively managed, and managers should maintain regular communication with employees. In addition, mentoring programs, career development opportunities, feedback mechanisms, and leadership development initiatives may strengthen employees' organizational commitment and engagement levels. Organizations should also cultivate supportive work environments by offering access to mental health services, stress management resources, mindfulness practices, and professional development opportunities.

5.3. Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations. First, the exclusive use of a survey method and the cross-sectional nature of the data limit the ability to establish causal relationships. Second, the findings are limited to employees working in educational institutions in Hatay, Türkiye, which may restrict the generalizability of the results. Additionally, difficulties encountered during the data collection process due to the earthquake may have affected the sample structure. Finally, the study focused primarily on selected demographic and psychological variables.

5.4. Recommendations for Future Research

Future research may examine the relationship between POS and WE in different sectors and cultural contexts to improve the generalizability of the

findings. Longitudinal studies may also provide a deeper understanding of causal relationships among the variables. Although the analysis results revealed that the serial mediation of WLB and PWB in the relationship between POS and WE was significant, the direct effect was not completely eliminated. This finding suggests that POS may also influence WE through alternative mechanisms beyond the pathways examined in this study. Therefore, future studies may examine alternative mediating and moderating variables that could influence the relationship between POS and WE. Incorporating organizational-level variables and mixed-method research designs may contribute to more comprehensive and holistic findings.

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